

Corrosion Inhibition of Aluminium Metal By Schiff's Bases In Acidic Medium

Paper Id : 21031 Submission Date : 2025-11-01 Acceptance Date : 2025-11-21 Publication Date : 2025-11-25

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DOI:10.5281/zenodo.18194081

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Poonam Choudhary
Research Scholar
Department Of Chemistry
SKD University
HanumangarhRajasthan,
India

V. K. Swami
Research Supervisor
Department Of Chemistry
SKD University
Hanumangarh, Rajasthan,
India

Abstract

The Schiff base N,N'-bis[(3,4-dihydroxy-5-nitrophenyl)methylidene]thiourea (BDHNPMTU) synthesized by condensation of 3,4-dihydroxy-5-nitro-benzaldehyde and thiourea. The structure of Schiff base was fully characterized by elemental analysis, FT-IR and UV-Vis methods. The inhibition effect of BDHNPMTU towards the corrosion on aluminium in 1M HCl was investigated using weight loss measurement technique. Results showed that BDHNPMTU is an effective inhibitor for aluminium corrosion in 1.0 M HCl solution. It was found that when the concentration of the inhibitors was increased the inhibition efficiency was increased, too. Adsorption of the inhibitor on the aluminium surface followed Langmuir adsorption isotherm. In 4 hr time duration Maximum inhibition efficiency (99%) is shown at highest concentration of inhibitor ($5 \times 10^{-5} \text{M}$).

Keywords

BDHNPMTU, Corrosion, Inhibition Efficiency, Aluminium, Weight Loss Measurement.

Introduction

Corrosion is the deterioration or destruction of metals and alloys by the reaction with its environment. The environment could be of any type such as atmosphere, water, seawater, acid alkaline, steam, gases, soil and liquid metals etc. It is a constant and continuous problem, often difficult to eliminate completely (1).

Aluminium is soft, malleable and ductile metal with very high thermal and electric conductivity [2-3]. Aluminium is resistant toward the influence of atmosphere and many chemicals, however, it is known that in aggressive media it is susceptible to corrosion. Corrosion is a very common phenomenon in industries and it has wide amount of interest because of its hazardous nature on metals [4]. Due to the excellent mechanical properties and low cost, aluminium is extensively used as a constructional material in many industries. However, when exposed to the corrosive industrial environment, it is easily corroded. Normally, acid solutions such as hydrochloric acid are widely used such as in acid pickling, industrial cleaning, oil well cleaning, etc. The use of inhibitor is one of the most practical methods for protection against corrosion to protect metal dissolution and acid consumption [5]. Organic compounds containing a heteroatom (O, N and S) in their structure act as good corrosion inhibitors. They form a coordination bond with vacant d orbital of metal and form a protective layer on the surface of metal. The effectiveness of these organic molecules is based on their ability to form a protective layer by several mechanisms (i.e. adsorption, polymerization). [6-17].

Recently the use of synthetic inhibitors has created environmental problems due to its toxicity properties. Thus it is important and necessary to develop low cost and environmentally safe corrosion inhibitors [18-19].

Objective of study

The aim of the present paper is to evaluate the anticorrosive properties of Schiff base (BDHNPMTU) on aluminium corrosion in a strong acidic media.

Review of Literature

Schiff bases form an important class of the most widely used organic compounds and has a wide variety of applications in many fields including analytical, biological and inorganic chemistry [20]. Schiff bases containing the azomethine or imine ($-\text{RC}=\text{N}-$) and are usually formed by the condensation of primary amine with an active carbonyl compound. This product was first formed by German chemist noble prize winner Huggo Schiff [21]. Schiff bases of aliphatic aldehydes are relatively unstable and readily polymerizable [22-23]. While those of aromatic aldehydes having effective conjugation are more stable [24-25].

Figure 1: Schiff base

Schiff bases easily form stable complex with transition metals due to this reason they are also have corrosion inhibitory property. The Schiff base of thiourea (BDHNPMTU) is nontoxic, soluble in aqueous media, relatively cheap and easy to produce at high purity. These properties would justify the use of Schiff base of thiourea as corrosion inhibitor.

Furthermore , in recent papers we have reported the beneficial effect exerted by several Schiff's bases i.e. triazole derivatives, imidazole, 4-((2-thiophenecarboxylic acid hydrazide) methylene) benzoic acid (HD2), 2-(salicylideneimino) thiophenol (SITP), (NE)-N-(furan-2- ylmethylidene)-4-({4-[E)-(furan-2-ylmethylidene) amino] phenyl} ethyl) aniline (SB), L-serine based Schiff base on aluminium corrosion in acidic media[26-37]. We have found that protective efficiency of the Schiff bases on aluminium corrosion strongly depends on the size and electronic effect of the substituents in molecule.

Analysis

Synthesis and characterization of BDHNPMTU:

Synthesis of BDHNPMTU:

All the reagents used in this study were of analytical grade. 3,4-dihydroxy-5-nitro- benzaldehyde, thiourea and glacial acetic acid were of obtained from (SLR, India). The BDHNPMTU was synthesized and characterized on the basis of past various research studies done so far [38-47]

The N,N'-bis[(3,4-dihydroxy-5-nitrophenyl)methylidene]thiourea (BDHNPMTU) was synthesized from 3,4-dihydroxy-5-nitro-benzaldehyde and thiourea in equal molar ratio in ethanol (20ml) in presence of glacial acetic acid(2ml). The content was refluxed for about 4-5 hours at 70°C with water condenser. On cooling the contents the dark brown coloured solid (M.P.110°C) separated out. The same was filtered, washed with 50% ethanol, recrystallised in ethanol. The method of synthesis is summarized in Figure (1).

Figure 2

Characterization of BDHNPMTU:

The structure of compound was characterized by elemental analysis, IR and electronic studies. The elemental study shows the presence of C (44.34%), H (2.48%), N (13.79%), O (31.50%) and S (7.89%) in the compound. Absence of a $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ band of aldehyde and presence of $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ band occurred at $1690\text{-}1640\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the IR spectra of BDHNPMTU indicating the condensation between aldehyde group of 3,4-dihydroxy-5-nitro-benzaldehyde and amino group of thiourea. In IR spectra of BDHNPMTU different band also observed such as -O-H str. between $3500\text{-}3700\text{ cm}^{-1}$, broad band of N-H str. between $3100\text{-}3400\text{ cm}^{-1}$, -N-O str. of -NO_2 group at $1515\text{-}1560\text{ cm}^{-1}$, $1345\text{-}1385\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and C-S str. of $\text{C}=\text{S}$ group at $\sim 725, \sim 1100\text{ cm}^{-1}$. In the electronic spectrum of BDHNPMTU $n\text{-}\Pi^*$ absorption peak of azomethine group were observed at 310.5, 320.5, 341.5, 354, 370 nm and $\Pi^*\text{-}\Pi^*$ peak of benzene ring observed at 249.5nm.

Experimental:

For the mass loss study rectangular aluminium specimens of size 3.0cm x 2.0cm x 0.1 cm was employed with a small hole of about 0.02 cm. diameter near the upper edge were employed. The specimens were mechanically polished with

different grades of emery paper; they were degreased in absolute alcohol, dried in acetone and stored in moisture free desiccators before their use in adsorption studies. All the chemicals employed were of analytical grade and the corresponding solutions were prepared in double distilled water. .01M inhibitor solution was used for corrosion study.

Each specimen was suspended by a V- shaped glass hook made by ne capillary glass tube and immersed in a glass beaker containing 50 ml of test solution at room temperature. After the exposure of sufficient time the test specimen was taken out, cleaned under running water and dried in oven, after drying specimens weighted. The variation in mass loss was followed at an interval for 4 hours to 72 hours in 1M HCl as shown in the tables 1.

The percentage corrosion inhibition efficiency was calculated as

$$\eta\% = 100 (\Delta M_U - \Delta M_i) / \Delta M_U$$

Where, ΔM_U = Mass loss of metal in uninhibited solution.

ΔM_i = Mass loss of metal in inhibited solution.

The degree of Surface coverage (Θ) of metal specimen by inhibitor was calculated as:

$$\Theta = (\Delta M_U - \Delta M_i) / \Delta M_U$$

The corrosion rates can be calculated by the following equation:

$$\text{Corrosion rate (mm / yr)} = (\text{Mass loss} \times 87.6) / \text{DAT}$$

Where, D = density of aluminium

A = surface area of metal specimen T = time exposure

Result and Discussion

The inhibition of corrosion is a complex phenomenon and the efficiency of inhibitor depends on various factors. In this paper we discuss effect of two factors namely immersion time and inhibitor concentration. Immersion time can play a decisive role in the prevention of corrosion ability. BDHNPMTU have shown a decreasing in its inhibition performance by rising exposure time or immersion time. Corrosion rate values decrease as the concentration of inhibitor increases. Consequently, inhibition efficiency values increase with the increase the concentration of inhibitor and maximum Inhibition efficiency 99 % shown at 5% ($5 \times 10^{-4}M$) inhibitor concentration (4 hr). This is due to the adsorption of inhibitor on the aluminium surface. Adsorption of inhibitor obey Langmuir isotherm.

Table 1: Concentration of inhibitor (COI), mass loss, inhibition efficiency, surface coverage and corrosion rate for aluminium metal in presence of BDHNPMTU at different time interval

C O I(%)	4 hours				24 hours				48 hours				72 hours			
	ΔM (mg)	η (%)	Θ	CR (mm/yr)	ΔM (mg)	η (%)	Θ	CR (mm/yr)	ΔM (mg)	η (%)	Θ	CR (mm/yr)	ΔM (mg)	η (%)	Θ	CR (mm/yr)
blank	.281	.2718	2.998	2.268
1	.04	80	.80	.16	.08	70	.7	.05	.56	80	.8	.19	.62	72	.72	.14
2	.03	85	.85	.12	.06	77	.77	.04	.36	88	.88	.12	.37	83.6	.836	.08
3	.005	97	.97	.02	.03	89	.89	.02	.24	91	.91	.81	.28	87.2	.872	.06
5	.002	99	.99	.008	.01	96	.96	.006	.17	94	.94	.05	.16	92.7	.927	.03

Figure 3: The graph inhibition efficiency v/s concentration of inhibitor (%) at different time interval for aluminium in 1 M HCl

Figure 4: The presence of protecting layer of BDHNPMTU on aluminium surface in 1M HCl

Conclusion

The efficiency of synthesized Schiff base BDHNPMTU as corrosion inhibition for aluminium in acidic media have been studies. Results obtained from weight loss technique indicate that Schiff base act as efficient inhibitor for aluminium corrosion in acidic media. The graph between inhibition efficiency and concentration shows that the inhibition efficiency increases with concentration of inhibitor.

Figure 5: IR spectrum of BDHNPMTU

Acknowledgement

Special thanks to Department of chemistry and the Principal, Govt. Lohia (PG) College, Churu provided facility of Research Laboratory.

References

1. Rani B E and Basu B B J, *International Journal of Corrosion*, (2012).
2. Meija J, Copen T B, Berglund M, Brand W A, Bievre P D and Prohaska T, *Pure and Applied chemistry*, 88(3) (2016) 265-291.
3. Moret, Marc-Etienne, Zhang, Limei, Peters and Jonas C, *Journal of American Chemical society*, 135(10) (2013) 3792-3795.

4. Uhlig H H and Revie R W, *Corrosion and Corrosion Control*, Wiley, New York, (1985).
5. Sorkabi H A, Seifzadeh D and Hosseini M G, *Corrosion Science*, 50(2008) 3363.
6. Fareles F and Ramirez A, *International Journal of Electrochemical Science*, 5(2010) 797.
7. Joseph X and Rajendra N, *International Journal of Electrochemical Science*, 6(2011) 348.
8. Gogoi P K and Barhai B, *International Journal of Electrochemical Science*, 6(2011) 136.
9. Quraishi M A and Jamal D, *Journal of Applied Electrochemistry*, 32(2002) 425.
10. Elayyachy M, El-Idrissi A and Hammouti B, *Corrosion science*, 48(2006) 2470.
11. Emregul K C and Hayvali M, *Corrosion Science*, 40(1998) 391.
12. Mernari B, Elattari H, Traisnel M, Bentiss F and Lagrenee M, *Corrosion Science*, 40(1998)391.
13. Wang L, *Corrosion Science*, 43(2001) 2281.
14. Azhar M E, Mernari M Traisnel M, Bentiss F and Lagrenee, *Corrosion Science*, 43(2001) 2229.
15. Negam N A, Yousef M A and Tawfik S M, *Recent Patents on Corrosion Science*, 2013(3)1.
16. Kuznetsov Y I and Kazansky L P, *Russian chemistry review*, 77(2008) 219-232.
17. Aljourani J, raeissi K and Golozar M A, *Corrosion Science*, 51(2009) 1836-1843.
18. Lotto R T, Lotto C A and Popoola A P I, *Journal of Materials and Environmental Science*, 3(2012) 885-894.
19. Ladha D G, Naik U J and Shah N K, *Journal of Materials and Environmental Science*, 4(2013) 701-708.
20. Hossain M S, Roy P K, Zakaria C M and Kudrat-E-Zahan M, *International Journal of Chemical Studies*, 6(1) (2018)19-31.
21. Cimerman Z, Miljani'c S and Gali'c N, *Croatica Chemica Acta*, 73(1) (2000) 81-95.
22. Arjuman B L, Kudrat-E-Zahan M, Bashar M A, Haque M M and Islam M Q S, *International Journal of Chemical Study*, 2(6)(2015) 38-41.
23. Costes J P, Dahan F, Fernandez M B F, Garcia M I F and Deibe A M G, *Inorganic Chimica Acta*, (1998) 27473.
24. Kaczmarek M T, Jastrza R, Hoáderna-KĆdzia E and Radecka- Paryzek W. *Inorganic Chimica Acta*, 362 (2009) 3127.
25. Mukherjee P, Sengupta O, Drew M G B and Ghosh A. *Inorganic Chimica Acta* (2009) 285-362.
26. Neelakantana M A, Rusalraj F, Dharmaraja J, Johnsonraja S, Jeyakumar T and Pillai M S, *Spectrochemical Acta*, 71 (2008)1599.
27. Sudheer, Quraishi M A, *Corrosion Science*, 70(2013) 161-169.
28. Qiang Y, Zhang S, Xu S and Li W, *Journal of Colloid and Interface Science*, 472(2016) 852-859.
29. Zhang J, Lin Z, Han G C, Chen S L and Chen Z, *Applied Surface Science*, 389(2016) 601- 608 .
30. Monticelli C, Balbo A, Esvan J, Chiavari C, Martini C, Zanotto F, Marvelli L and Robbiola L, *Corrosion Science*, 148(2019) 144-148.
31. Issaadi S, Doudi T, Chafaa S, *Applied Surface Science*, 316(2014)582-589.
32. Mathur R, Pareek M and Swami V K, *Global Journal for Research Analysis*, 7(2) (2018) 2277-8160.
33. Pareek M, Pareek C and Swami V K, *Indian Journal of Research*, 7(6) (2018) 2250- 1991.
34. Pareek M and Swami V K, *Indian Journal of Research*, 7(7) (2018) 2250-1991.
35. Mathur R, Mathur P and Swami V K, *Global Journal for Research Analysis*, 6(12) (2017) 2277-8160.
36. Poonia R, Kumar S and Swami V K, *International Journal of Chemical Science*, 10(4) (2012) 1897-1904.
37. Poonia R and Swami V K, *International Journal of Chemical Science*, 13(2013) 1888.
38. Kuruvilla M, John S and Joseph A, *Journal of Bio- and Tribo- Corrosion*, 2(19) (2016) 2- 10.
39. Meena L, Choudhary P, Varshney A K and varshney S, *International Journal of Chem Tech Research*, 11(07)(2018) 337-346.
40. Abirami M and Nadaraj V, *International Journal of Chem Tech research*, 6(4) (2014) 2534-2538.
41. Rizwana B and Lakshmi S, *International Journal of Chem Tech research*, 4(1) (2014) 464-473.

42. Xavier A and Srividhya N, *IOSR Journal of Applied Chemistry*, 7(11) (2014) 6-15.
43. Sakthilatha D, Deepa A and Rajavel R, *Synthesis and Reactivity in inorganic, Metal- Organic and Nano-Metal Chemistry*, 45(2015) 286-297.
44. Yadav G and Mani J V, *International Journal of Science and Research*, 4(2) (2015) 121- 127.
45. Al-Obaidi, *Journal of applicable Chemistry*, 1(3) (2012) 352-359.
46. Kumar Ramesh and Swani V. K., *Inovation the Research comcept vol. X(3)*, 2025, 18-23.
47. Kumar Ramesh and Swani V. K., *Asian Resonance* 14(2) 2025, 19-23.